

Pathways to Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research: the SHAPE-ID Toolkit

Find tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Reflective Tools Collection

for Inter- and Transdisciplinary Research

Abstract

SHAPE-ID partners have drawn upon their experience of inter- and transdisciplinary research to provide tailored reflective tools that support individuals and groups to consider the most important issues when collaborating in, reviewing, funding, and supporting inter- and transdisciplinary research.

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SHAPE-ID consortium members

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Online source – SHAPE-ID Toolkit

This publication is an extract of the SHAPE-ID Toolkit. For a general overview, visit: [10.5281/zenodo.4743703](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/files/zenodo.4743703).

The Toolkit provides tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Contributors & Co-producers

The Reflective tools collection is based on discussions with and inputs from the SHAPE-ID consortium members, namely Anna Buchner, Maureen Burgess, Bianca Vienni Baptista, Caitriona Curtis, Isabel Fletcher, Giorgia Galvini, Catherine Lyall, Maciej Maryl, Jane Ohlmeyer, Christian Pohl, Andrea Ricci, Carlo Sessa, Jack Spaapen, Sibylle Studer, Doireann Wallace, Piotr Wciślik, Keisha Taylor Wesselink, Declan Whelan-Curtin.

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I. Reflective tool for researchers & knowledge co-creators I

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III. Reflective tool for reviewers of inter- or transdisciplinary research proposals

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IV. Reflective tool for research funders

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V. Reflective tool for higher education institutions

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Reflective tool for researchers & knowledge co-creators I

When to use?

When considering engaging in collaborative research

Ask yourself...

- Why am I considering collaborating?
- Does this project really require an ID/TD approach?
- What do I want to achieve through this collaboration?
- Who should I work with to achieve these goals?
- What do I bring to this project? What do others bring?
- What kinds of collaboration will this project involve - between different disciplines, fields of research, institutions or sectors of society?
- How do others understand my research?
- How open am I to these different perspectives on my research?
- Are there important power imbalances between different individuals/groups with the project?
- Has this type of collaboration been done before?
- Have these individuals or groups worked together previously?
- Is there a shared language/approach that we can build upon?
- Do all partners have the same understanding of what is involved in collaborative research?
- Am I prepared to put the effort into building the relationships necessary for successful collaboration?

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Reflective tool for researchers & knowledge co-creators II

When to use?

When beginning a collaborative research project

Ask yourself...

- Does everyone know who all the partners are and what they will bring to the project?
- Have all partners been able to contribute to the design of this project?
- Do the research questions frame the topic in ways that are engaging and fruitful for all partners?
- Has a shared understanding of the project's aims and purpose been explicitly stated? And agreed upon?
- Is the research design predefined in the project proposal or to be negotiated among the group?
- What model of collaboration has been drawn upon when planning this project – is it described as interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary or something else?
- Will there be opportunities for partners to learn about each other's research methods and perspectives on the topic?
- How will you avoid making assumptions about partners' approaches to the topic?
- How will you ensure that no one group or perspective dominates the research process?
- Are there mechanisms in place to enable the ongoing exchange of ideas and opinions across disciplines and sectors?
- Will there be regular meetings that all project partners are expected to attend?
- Will all partners have to opportunity to provide feedback on project development and outputs? What happens if they cannot reach consensus?
- Have you agreed rules for co-authorship of these outputs?
- What does success look like for this project?

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Reflective tool for reviewers of inter- or transdisciplinary research proposals

When to use?

When evaluating the feasibility and impact of an inter- or transdisciplinary approach in research proposals

Ask yourself...

- How was the problem formulated? Were several experts (disciplines/practitioners) involved in the problem formulation or is such an involvement still planned?
- How diverse are the disciplines, methods and researchers and how suitable is the combination of disciplines?
- Is stakeholder involvement relevant to the problem and if yes, is there an appropriate plan for stakeholder/user identification and engagement from the outset of the project?
- Is there a clear justification for the choice of disciplines based on the needs of the research questions?
- Is the study sufficiently anchored in relevant literature and – in the case of transdisciplinary research – embedded in an analysis of the specific context?
- Does the methodology provide moments for joint reflection and for iterative adaptation?
- How will communication be tackled?
- Does it describe how the disciplines involved will be integrated (in the design and conduct of the research as well as in subsequent publications) and how this relates to the type of interdisciplinarity involved; does it demonstrate how the quality of integration will be assured?
- How is the collaboration organised – is there an understanding of the challenges of inter- and transdisciplinary integration, including methodological integration, and the 'human' side of fostering interactions and communication, and an effective strategy to achieve this?
- If the project includes stakeholder involvement: is co-producing knowledge with stakeholders envisaged, and are potential outcomes for stakeholders outlined?
- Is the leadership role and management strategy to deliver the desired outcomes clearly articulated and budgeted for?
- Do the researchers involved have demonstrable inter- and transdisciplinary skills, experience, and networks?
- In particular, is there evidence of inter- and transdisciplinary leadership?

- Does the proposal budget for, and justify, the additional resources needed?
- Is it clear how inter- and trans-disciplinarity will be reflected in the project outputs and outcomes?
- Is there a reflection about societal impact from the outset of the project? Is it clear how effects on society – as perceived by different involved parties – will be documented (and facilitated)?
- Is there a reflection about risks? Is the research setting flexible and resilient in the sense that unexpected events and group dynamics can be handled?

Several commentators have previously suggested sets of questions that reviewers might adopt to probe quality indicators which have informed this checklist; see [Lyll and King's report on international good practice in the peer review of interdisciplinary research](#) for further details.

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Reflective tool for research funders

When to use?

When preparing to fund collaborative research

Ask yourself...

- Were researchers across a spectrum of disciplines, and individuals from other sectors, fully involved in the development of this funding scheme or call?
- Were scholars with experience in inter- and trans-disciplinary research involved in the development of this funding scheme or call?
- Does the research call use language that encourages multiple approaches to the topic?
- If the proposed research is aimed at solving societal problems, does it leave the framing of these problems open, or does it suggest narrow framings that for instance assume they need technical solutions?
- Do your processes assume that each project or work package will be led by one senior academic? What might this mean for potential integration across the project?
- Does your call ask for an explanation of an application's underlying concept of interdisciplinarity or transdisciplinarity?
- Does your call ask them to clarify how key challenges of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research – like problem framing, integration or exploring how to have impact – will be addressed?
- Has the research call been widely advertised with enough time so that those who have not previously applied can submit a credible application?
- Is it easy for potential applicants to get advice about the aims of the funding scheme and how to develop a high-quality application?
- Would you consider offering seed corn funding to launch projects in new interdisciplinary directions?
- Or a two-stage process where feedback is given on outline applications before a full application is submitted?
- Do your funding schemes allow for the extra time necessary to undertake high-quality collaborative research due, for example, to larger research groups and greater uncertainties?

- Do they also allow for the extra costs incurred when undertaking collaborative research, such as initial events to develop partnerships and to jointly develop problem framings, or facilitation to improve communication, to find common ground or for learning and integration processes to happen within larger projects?
- Who does your organisation use to evaluate collaborative research proposals? Are they experienced collaborative researchers, familiar with best practice in ID/TD evaluation?
- Are there ways in which you could help collaborative researchers develop networks and communities?
- How else do you support collaborative researchers and share best practice?

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Reflective tool for higher education institutions

When to use?

When evaluating existing institutional supports for inter- or transdisciplinary researchers and projects

Ask yourself...

- Do you provide training in key collaborative research skills, such as managing diverse groups?
- What opportunities are there for researchers from under-represented groups or disciplines to develop skills to lead collaborative research teams?
- Do you provide creative, interactive spaces between disciplines' territories, such as cafeterias, coffee rooms, hallway alcoves, that are conducive to informal conversations?
- Do you show flexibility in grouping or regrouping individuals by area or theme of research, as interests evolve, so that they can interact outside of meetings?
- Are there opportunities for researchers from multiple departments to come together and explore a new research area, e.g. through externally facilitated retreats or workshops?
- Is advice about relevant funding schemes and how to develop a high-quality grant application readily available to all researchers, including those who are not yet tenured or on short-term contracts?
- Are there small amounts of internal (seed corn) funding available to allow researchers to develop their research networks, or pilot new research ideas?
- Can budgets, time and other resources be readily and equitably shared across administrative units?
- Do your administrative units all use the same processes, for example when signing off on research proposals?
- Do you provide resources to sustain collaborations beyond the life of a specific project e.g. to organise meetings or visit partners?
- Do you celebrate or formally recognise interdisciplinary successes and cite them at high-level institutional events and in publications?
- How well do your recruitment and promotion criteria evaluate collaborative researchers?
- What kind of job security do interdisciplinary researchers have in your organisation? How does that compare with disciplinary experts?

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